

1 390, 1 248, 1 140, 1 080, 970 and 870 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 240 (3.7) and 295 (2.2); δ 5.9 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 5.7 (1H, m), 4.9 (1H), 2.2 (3H, s), 2.1 (3H) and 0.9–1.2 (15 H). Acetylation with Ac_2O –sodium acetate (on reflux) gave the diacetate, m.p. 180° (lit.⁷ 180–82°); M^+ : 484 (Found: C, 69.34; H, 7.70; CH_3CO , 17.25. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_7$ requires: C, 69.42; H, 7.43; CH_3CO (2 acetyl groups), 17.76%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 740, 1 720, 1 690, 1 660, 1 590, 1 390, 1 170, 980 and 870 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH) (log ϵ) 240 (3.9) and 320 (1.8); δ 5.9 (1H, d, J 3.5 Hz), 5.7 (1H, m), 4.9 (1H), 2.2 (3H, s), 2.1 (6H), 0.9–1.3 (15H). It was thus characterised as hexanor-cucurbitacin I.

Further elution of chromatogram with benzene–methanol (70 : 30) yielded a solid E, m.p. 140–42°, M^+ : 442 (Found: C, 70.61; H, 7.64; CH_3CO , 10.11. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_6$ requires: C, 70.58; H, 7.69; CH_3CO (1 acetyl group), 10.18%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 3 350, 1 740, 1 715, 1 690, 1 660, 1 587, 1 385, 1 040, 980 and 970; λ_{max} (EtOH) (log ϵ) 240 (3.5) and 295 (1.6); δ 5.9 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 5.7 (1H, m), 5.0 (1H, m), 2.4 (3H, s), 2.22 (3H, s) and 0.9–1.35 (15 H). It was found identical with monoacetate of D and 16-*O*-acetylhexanor-cucurbitacin I (m.m.p., m.p., ir, uv, nmr).

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Nickel with Diphenylcarbazone in Presence of Pyridine

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DIPHENYLCARBAZONE has long been known as a reagent for the detection and determination of a number of metals^{1–3}. It forms chelate complexes with many heavy metals^{4,5}. Nickel(II)

forms a pink coloured 1 : 2 complex⁶ with it, but the colour of the complex fades rather rapidly. In the present investigation, it is found that in presence of pyridine, nickel(II) forms with diphenylcarbazone a purple coloured complex which is extractable into methyl isobutyl ketone. When pyridine is replaced by other heterocyclic bases like picolines and collidine, the sensitivity of the colour reaction is much less. Thus, it is found that diphenylcarbazone and pyridine make a suitable ligand pair for the determination of nickel(II) spectrophotometrically. This forms the basis of the present method which has proved to be very simple and sensitive.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path was used for absorbance measurements. pH values were determined with a Elico LI-10 pH meter.

A stock solution of nickel was prepared from $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR) in distilled water and standardised gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime reagent⁶. Solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. A 0.2% solution of diphenylcarbazone (B.D.H.) in absolute alcohol and a 5% pyridine solution in distilled water were employed as reagents. Solutions of 0.2 *M* boric acid, 0.2 *M* sodium hydroxide and 0.2 *M* potassium chloride were prepared to constitute the required buffer. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade salts.

Procedure: To an aliquot of the test solution containing 0.5 to 10 μg of nickel, 5% pyridine (2 ml) and buffer solution (2 ml) were added and the total volume was made upto 10 ml so that pH of the aqueous phase maintained around 9.0. To it 0.2% diphenylcarbazone solution (1 ml) and then MIBK (10 ml) were added and the resulting mixture was shaken for 5 min in a separatory funnel. The organic layer was separated and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 530 nm against the reagent blank. The nickel content in unknown solutions was computed from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The nickel(II)–diphenylcarbazone–pyridine complex system exhibits maximum absorbance at 530 nm when measured against the reagent blank and obeys Beer's law over the range 0.05–1 ppm of Ni^{II} . The optimum concentration range is found to be 0.1–1 ppm of Ni^{II} . The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction is 0.000 61 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity $9.62 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 530 nm.

The results of extraction studies of nickel–diphenylcarbazone–pyridine system show that

nickel can be quantitatively extracted into MIBK in the pH range 8.4–9.5. Below and above this pH range, the extraction of nickel was incomplete. The extracted species exhibited constant and maximum absorption, when the pH of the aqueous phase was maintained within this range. Buffer solutions constituted by 0.2 M H_3BO_3 , 0.2 M KCl and 0.2 M NaOH were employed during the investigation.

The effect of varying the reagent concentration on extraction of nickel was studied. It is found that 0.2% diphenylcarbazone solution (1 ml) and 5% pyridine (2 ml) are adequate for complete extraction of the complex at pH range 8.4–9.5 for the range of the concentration of Ni^{II} (0.5–10 μg) determined. A 1–10% solution of pyridine can be used without any effect on the values of absorbance. The extraction of nickel was incomplete at the concentration of diphenylcarbazone less than 0.1%. Increased diphenylcarbazone concentration (0.5%) produces no increase in the absorption values.

Various solvents such as benzene, toluene, amyl alcohol, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane and MIBK were tested for the extraction of nickel complex, but MIBK was found to be the most effective one. With 10 ml of MIBK, the complex was recovered to the extent of 99.99% by a single extraction, whereas with other solvents, it was found to be less than 95%. The complex was stable for more than 15 h in MIBK. For complete extraction of the complex, 5 min shaking period was adequate. The absorbance of the complex is independent of temperature in the range 15–35°.

Job's method of continuous variation⁷ and mole-ratio method⁸ were employed to establish the nickel–diphenylcarbazone ratio in the presence of pyridine. The results indicated that a 1 : 2 complex between Ni and diphenylcarbazone is formed. The complex seems to have been stabilised by mixed ligation with pyridine.

Effect of diverse ions: A number of representative ions were examined for their interference in the determination of nickel (5 μg) by the recommended procedure. The tolerance limit was set at the amount required to cause less than 3% error in the recovery of nickel. Estimation of Ni^{II} in presence of Sn^{II} , Sn^{IV} , Bi^{III} and Sb^{III} was done using tartrate as masking agent, and in presence of Cu^{II} and Co^{II} , thiourea and thiocyanate, respectively, were used for masking. In presence of V^{V} , the mixture was allowed to stand for 1 h before extraction. It was found that Zn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Rh^{III} , cyanide and EDTA interfered seriously. The following foreign ions (I) caused no interference at I : Ni weight ratio : Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} , ≤ 4 ; Ag^I , Mn^{II} , Mo^{VI} , Cu^{II} , Sn^{II} , Sn^{IV} and Bi^{III} ≤ 5 ; Au^{III} , Cd^{II} and As^{III} ≤ 20 ; V^{V} , Sb^{III} and Pb^I ≤ 10 ; Co^{II} , Hg^{II} , Ru^{III} and Pd^{II} ≤ 2 ; Pt^{IV} ≤ 7 ; Cr^{VI} ≤ 100 ; oxalate, fluoride, thiocyanate and phosphate ≤ 100 ; citrate, tartrate, thiourea,

sulphite, bromide and iodide ≥ 200 ; thiosulphate ≤ 20 .

Applications: The method was applied to determine nickel from the following standard samples. Methods of dissolution of the materials followed by separations, wherever necessary, to obtain the final solution for its use in the determination of nickel by the recommended procedure have been summarised below.

(i) Cupronickel alloy : To the alloy (0.455 g), a mixture of water (10 ml), concentrated H_2SO_4 (1 ml) and concentrated HNO_3 (2 ml) was added to dissolve the alloy. When the dissolution was complete, the oxides of nitrogen was boiled off and the solution diluted to 100 ml with 0.3 M HCl. The solution was heated and H_2S was passed through it to precipitate out all the copper present in the solution. From the filtrate, H_2S was boiled off and the solution was made upto 250 ml. The solution was used for the determination of nickel.

(ii) Nickel steel : To the nickel steel (0.954 g), 8N HNO_3 (15 ml) and then concentrated HCl (2 ml) were added and the mixture was boiled gently till the dissolution the sample was complete. The solution was diluted to 100 ml and to it NH_4Cl and NH_4OH were added to precipitate out all the iron present in the solution. The precipitate was filtered and washed carefully and the filtrate was heated to reduce the volume. The solution was then made slightly acidic with dilute HCl and the volume made upto 100 ml. The solution was used for the determination of nickel.

The results, which are the average of three determinations of each sample are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL IN STANDARD SAMPLES*

Samples no. and composition (%)	Nickel found (%)
Cupronickel alloy (19e)	
Cu 67, Fe 0.83, Mn 0.80, Ni 31.2	30.9
Nickel steel (22a)	
Ni 2.87	2.86

* Obtained from B.A.S. Ltd., England.

Precision and accuracy: A standard solution containing 5 μg of nickel was estimated (10 times) by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.819 with a standard deviation of 0.0061 absorbance unit and a relative error of $\pm 0.7\%$. The limit of detection was found to be 1 part of nickel in 3×10^7 .

A comparative study with other reagents shows (Table 2) that the present method is by far the most sensitive method in the determination of nickel. The method is very simple and rapid providing good recovery of nickel in presence of most of the common ions. The total operation time in each run is 10–15 min.

TABLE 2—COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SOME CALORIMETRIC METHODS FOR NICKEL USING DIFFERENT REAGENTS

Reagents	λ_{\max} nm	Molar absorptivity $\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$
Dimethylglyoxime + oxidising agent ^a	445	1.89×10^4	0.0042
Diethyldithiocarbamate ^a	325	3.26×10^4	0.0018
o-Mercaptoacetacetanilide + 7-picolins ^b	615	5.21×10^3	0.05
Rubeanic acid + quinoline ^c	390	8.46×10^3	0.0058
Diphenylcarbazone + pyridine ^d	590	9.62×10^4	0.00061

^aRef. 9. ^bRef. 10. ^cRef. 11. ^dPresent work.

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Some Titrimetric Applications of N-Iodophthalimide in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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RECENTLY, N-chlorophthalimide and N-bromophthalimide have been developed as better and stabler oxidimetric titrants than most other oxidants of similar type^{1,2}. A search through the literature has revealed that their iodine analogue, viz. N-iodophthalimide (NIP) has not been used as an oxidimetric titrant so far although it has been used in clinical pharmacology³. Therefore, we thought it would be interesting to explore the possibility of employing NIP as an oxidant for titrations in aqueous acetic acid medium. In this communication, we report the results of determination of 37 reductants of diverse types using NIP as the titrant in aqueous acetic acid medium.

Experimental

N-Iodophthalimide (NIP) was prepared by iodinating phthalimide using freshly prepared ICl as

per the literature method⁴. Phthalimide (15.0 g) was dissolved in minimum quantity of 10 M potassium hydroxide (20 ml). The solution was cooled to 5° in an ice-salt-bath and a previously cooled solution of ICl (20 ml) dissolved in acetonitrile (50 ml) was added slowly in small portions with stirring. Care was taken to keep the temperature of the reaction mixture always below 5°. The greenish yellow crystals of NIP formed were collected and washed with cold water-acetonitrile mixture (1 : 1, v/v) and finally with cold dry acetonitrile. The solid sample was dried in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide, the yield being about (85%), m.p. 225° (lit. 226°) (Found : I, 46.52. calcd. ; I, 46.32%). The purity of NIP was checked by an iodometric method, in which a known weight of the sample (0.05 g) was allowed to react with excess of potassium iodide (0.5 g) in acetic acid medium and the liberated iodine was titrated with standard thiosulphate.

NIP was found to be sparingly soluble in water undergoing hydrolysis with the liberation of iodine, and soluble in acetic acid (solubility, 10.2 g/kg at 30°). Approximately 0.05 N (~0.025 M) solution of NIP was prepared in anhydrous acetic acid (500 ml) by dissolving dry NIP (3.4 g) and kept in an amber coloured bottle; such a solution being reasonably stable to meet the requirements for an ideal titrant for use in non-aqueous media. The stock solution of NIP was standardised iodometrically as usual before use.

The following 37 reductants were chosen for titrations using NIP : As^{III}, sulphite, ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, hydrazine, benzhydrazide, isoniazid, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide, thiosemicarbazide, thioacetamide, thiourea, aniline, phenol, oxine, anthranilic acid, oxinates of Mg^{II}, Al^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and La^{III}, anthranilates of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II}, and thiosemicarbazides of Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II}. The metal oxinates, anthranilates and thiosemicarbazides were prepared by the literature methods⁵⁻⁸. Standard solutions of all the 37 reductants listed above were prepared in appropriate solvents as described earlier^{9,10}. The strengths of these reductant solutions were checked by standard methods^{9,10}.

Direct visual titrations were unsuccessful for anthranilic acid and its metal derivatives, and thiosemicarbazide and its metal derivatives. All the other reductants were determined by direct visual titration using quinoline yellow or amaranth as indicator. The usual procedures were used for both direct and excess-back titrations.

Results and Discussion

The results of the titrations are presented in Table 1 (direct titrations) and Table 2 (excess-back-titrations). During the reaction with the reductant, NIP is reduced to phthalimide,

